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PREAMBLE	
<p>Every book on management extols the virtues of management skills and techniques; every lecturer at every conference recognizes that the greater use of these techniques could, almost overnight, improve the efficiency of every organization by leaps and bounds.</p> <p>Management technique is a recognized method for analyzing or solving a recognized type of management problem in a detailed systematic way. Every society recognizes how managers face countless problems every day but many of them, on closer inspection, are found to be just variations on a few themes – themes that managers all over the world would recognize as being typical management problems. Also societies recognize that there are about a hundred techniques and that managers all over the world might recognize each one as being a particular, unique, step-by-step way of tackling management problems.</p> <p>This journal is therefore designed to help managers identify the appropriate skill and technique for any given type of problem that might confront him in his Business or Organization.</p> <p>Just as a manager is responsible for running his section efficiently, so is the chairman responsible for the efficiency of his company. It is largely in his hands whether the conditions in the company are favourable to the effective use of these techniques, or whether the enthusiasm of the new generation of managers is allowed to wither away. If conditions are favourable, individual managers will be encouraged to introduce these skills and techniques, but their individual efforts can be greatly magnified if the company appoints one man to encourage the use of these techniques and even further strengthen them if he develops a <i>systematic programme</i> for introducing them.</p> <p>Properly chosen and systematically introduced, correctly used in a receptive atmosphere, these techniques can substantially improve the efficiency of every organization.</p>	

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DIVIDEND POLICY AND ITS INFLUENCE ON THE VALUE OF THE ENTERPRISE:
THE NIGERIAN CAPITAL MARKET EXPERIENCE

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1.0 Introduction

The prime objective of a firm is to maximize wealth of its owners i.e. shareholders. Cash inflows are generated from the successful operation of business which are used for payment of dividends to its shareholders. Dividend paid represents a cash outflow which depletes the cash resources. The dividend decision is regarded as a financing decision since any cash dividend paid reduces the amount of cash available for investment by the firm. Dividends are periodic cash payments by the company to its shareholders. The dividend payable to the preference shareholders is usually fixed by the terms of the issue of preference shares. But the dividend on equity shares is payable at the discretion of the Board of Directors of the company.

The subject matter of dividend policy remains one of the most controversial issues in corporate finance. For more than half a century, financial economists have engaged in modeling and examining corporate dividend policy. Black (1976) hinted that, "The harder we look at the dividend picture, the more it seems like a puzzle, with pieces that don't fit together". In over

thirty years since then a vast amount of literature has been produced examining dividend policy. However, Frankfurter et al (2002) concluded in the same vein as Black and Scholes (1974) that: The dividend "puzzle" both as a share value-enhancing feature and as a matter of policy, is one of the most challenging topics of modern financial economics.

Forty years of research have not been able to resolve it. Research into dividend policy has shown not only that a general theory of dividend policy remains elusive, but also that corporate dividend practice varies over time, among firms and across countries developed, developing, underdeveloped and emerging capital markets.

Vasilios et al (2003) found that dividend policies in emerging markets differed from those in developed markets. They reported that dividend payout ratios in developing countries were only about two thirds of that of developed countries. Eriotis (2003) also observed low dividend yields for emerging markets. There has been emerging consensus that there is no single explanation of dividends.

According to Short et al. (2001) there is no reason to believe that corporate dividend policy is driven by a single goal.

In Determining Dividend Payout: When Should Companies Pay Dividends?, "a company should only pay dividends if it is unable to reinvest its cash at a higher rate than the shareholders (owners) of the business would be able to if the money was in their hands. If company ABC is earning 25% on equity with no debt, management should retain all of the earnings because the average investor probably won't find another company or investment that is yielding that kind of return." At the same time, an investor may require cash income for living expenses. In these cases, he is not interested in long-term appreciation of shares; he want a cheque with which he can pay the bills (Bhattacharyya, 2000). Dividends, like interest, are taxed at a person's individual tax rate. Capital gain taxes, on the other hand, are assessed according to the length of time an investor held his investment and can be as low as half the rate levied on dividends income. This difference in tax treatment is another reason many investors opt for long-term equity holdings that reinvest capital into the business instead of paying it out in the form of a dividend; by avoiding the double-taxation, they can compound their wealth at a faster rate. There is a significant political controversy over the fact that profits paid out as dividends are subject to double-taxation. The corporation paid income taxes on the profit it earned (original tax).

The owners of the business then take that profit out for their personal use in the form of a dividend and are taxed at personal income tax rates (second tax). In effect, they have paid the government twice.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The major problem associated with this research topic is the variability in dividend payments. Management are in a dilemma about whether to pay a large, small or zero percentage of their earnings as dividends or to retain them for future investments. This has come about as a result of the need for management to satisfy the various needs of shareholders. For instance, shareholders who need money now for profitable investment opportunities would like to receive high dividends now. On the other hand, shareholders who would like to invest in the future will prefer dividends to be retained by the company and reinvested.

1.2 Objective of the Study

The objectives of this study are to examine:

- (i) the need to invest in a firm with a policy of maintaining stable dividend, in terms of constant dividend payout ratio; constant dividend per share or a constant regular dividend plus a year extra, when earnings are high and corporate investment needs are sufficiently low and
- (ii) the maximization of shareholder's return so that the investment value is maximized.

1.3 Organization of the study

This study is divided into four segments - Introduction, Section II Legal and Theoretical Framework, Section III Justification for Dividend Policy and Section IV Conclusion and Recommendation

2.0 THEORETICAL AND LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF DIVIDEND POLICY

2.1 TYPES OF DIVIDEND

Dividend may be: (i) interim Dividend (ii) Final Dividend

Interim Dividend: An interim dividend is one which is declared before the declaration of the final dividend. Interim dividend is a dividend which is declared between two annual general

meetings.

The Board of directors may from time to time pay to the members such interim dividend as appears to it to be justified by the profits of the company. The directors must take into consideration the future prospects of the profits e.g. orders in hand, any seasonal element in business before declaration of interim dividend otherwise it may be considered payment out of capital. Cash resources, likelihood profitability of the company must also be taken into consideration while deciding to declare an interim dividend.

Final Dividend: At the end of the accounting period, the accounts of the company are prepared to ascertain the amount of profit earned by the company. The directors, taking into consideration the financial position of the company's future prospects, providing for resources, etc. decide to recommend to the shareholders at the annual general meeting the dividend to be paid to the shareholders.

Dividend on Preference Shares: The Articles of association of a company empower the directors to declare and pay both interim and final dividend on preference shares. Holders of preference shares are entitled to receive dividend before any dividend is paid to the equity shareholders as per the terms of the issue.

2.2 THEORIES OF COMPANY DIVIDEND POLICY

The important theories on Dividend Policies are discussed below:

Dividend Growth Valuation Model (Gordon Growth Model)

The dividends of most companies are expected to grow and evaluation of value shares based on dividend growth is often used in valuation of Shares - dividend valuation model assumes a constant level of growth in dividends in perpetuity. This model is known as Gordon Growth model. The formula is given below:

$$P_E = \frac{D_0(1+g)}{K_E - g}$$

$$K_E - g$$

Where,

PE = Market price per share (ex-dividend)

Do = Current year dividend

g = Constant annual growth rate of dividends

K_E = Cost of Equity Capital (Expected rate of return)

Assumptions: Gordon growth model using dividend capitalization is based on the following assumptions:

- ✓ Retained earnings represent the only source of financing.
- ✓ Rate of return is constant
- ✓ Growth rate of the firm is the product of retention ratio and its rate of return.
- ✓ Cost of Capital remains constant and is greater than growth rate
- ✓ The Company has perpetual life
- ✓ Tax does not exist

The implication of the model is that when the rate of return is greater than the discount rate, the price per share increases as the dividend ratio decreases and if the return is less than discount rate it is vice versa. The price per share remains unchanged where the rate of return and discount rate are equal.

In fact some companies, although earning profits, elect no pay dividends policy. This is a matter of deliberate financial policy, not a measure forced upon them by financial difficulties. The above theory of share evaluation can still be applied to these companies, since one day presumably they will start paying dividends. This is the only basis on which shareholders can obtain any returns from the company.

The reason for the rise in share prices is that with retention policies of the company, the rapid growth alters investors' expectations about the future size of dividends. At some time in the future, large dividends can be paid. Consequently it can be said that dividends determine the company's share price.

Walter's Valuation/Dividend Relevance Model

Walter argued that in the long-run the share prices reflect only the present value of expected dividends. Retentions influence stock price only through their effect on future dividends.

Walter has formulated this and used the dividend to optimize the wealth of an equity shareholder. His formula in determination of expected market price of a share is given below:

$$P = \frac{R_a}{D + R_c} (E - D)$$

Where,

- P = Market price of equity share
- D = Dividend per share
- E = Earning per share
- (E-D) = Retained earning per share
- R_a = Internal rate of return on investment
- R_c = Cost of Capital

If R_a is greater than, lower dividend will maximize the value per share and vice versa.

Assumptions: Walter's model is based on the following assumptions:

- All financing is done through retained earnings and external sources of funds like debt or new equity capital are not used.
- With additional investment undertaken, the firm's business risk does not change. It implies that firm's IRR and its cost of capital are constant.
- The firm has an infinite life and is a going concern.
- All earnings are either distributed as dividends or invested internally immediately.

There is no change in the key variables such as EPS and DPS.

In view of Walter, (1963) in the long-run the relationship between the rate of return on retained earnings, or return on investment and the rate of market expectation is important to the investors. We can summarize his idea into the following:

- In a company where the rate expected by investors is higher than market capitalization rate, shareholders would accept low dividends, and
- In a company where return on investment is lower than market capitalization rate, shareholders would prefer higher dividend so that they can utilize the funds so obtained elsewhere in more profitable opportunities.

Thus, according to him, the investment policy of a firm cannot be separated from its dividend policy as it affects the value of an enterprise. Retentions influence the share prices only through their effect on further dividends. The Walter's model implies that:

- a) The optimal payout ratio for a growth firm is nil.
- b) The optimal payout ratio for a normal firm is irrelevant.
- c) The optimal payout ratio for a declining firm is 100% Walter's formula is criticized for the reason that it does not consider all the factors affecting dividend policy and share prices.

Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM)

The model was introduced by Treynor (1961, 1962), Sharpe (1964), John Lintner (1965a, b) and Mossin (1966) independently, building on the earlier work of Harry Markowitz on diversification and Modern Portfolio Theory.

Capital Asset Pricing Model is used to determine a theoretically appropriate required rate of return of an asset if that asset is to be added to an already well diversified portfolio, given that asset is of a non-diversifiable risk (systemic risk or market risk) often represented by beta (β) in the financial industry as well as expected return of a theoretical risk free asset.

The market must price individual securities in relation to their security risk class and the Security Market Line (SLM) which describes a relationship between beta and the assets expected rate of return.

Consequently, the Security Market Line (SLM) allows the calculation of reward-to-risk ratio for any security in relation to that of the overall market.

The capital asset pricing model is also used in the valuation of shares. The following illustration will explain the procedure in using this method for valuation.

$$E(R) = R_f + \beta(R_m - R_f)$$

Where:

$E(R)$ = Expected rate of return on individual security

R_m = Market rate of return expected

R_f = Risk free return

β = Beta factor of investment

Modigliani and Miller - Irrelevancy Theory

Modigliani and Miller (1961) had argued that a firm's dividend policy has no effect on its value of assets for example, if the rate of dividend declared by a company is less, its retained earnings will increase and so also the net worth and vice versa. Their arguments is that the value of the firm is unaffected by dividend policy i.e. dividends are irrelevant to shareholders wealth. They built their argument on a number of assumptions the most important of which were:

- There are no personal or corporate income taxes.
- There are no stock floatation or transaction costs. Dividend policy has no effect on the firm's cost of equity. The firm's capital investment policy is independent of its dividend policy.
- Investors and managers have the same set of information (symmetric information) regarding future opportunities.

The reason given by MM is that the value of the firm is determined by its basic earnings power and its risk class, and therefore, that the firm's value depend on its asset investment policy rather than on how earnings are split between dividends and retained earnings. MM demonstrated, under a particular set of assumptions, that if a firm pays higher dividends, then it must sell more stocks to new investors, and that the share of the value of the company given up to new investors is exactly equal to the dividends paid out. The value of the firm was not determined by the amount of dividends paid, but rather by the earning power of the projects in which the firm invested its money.

The argument used by MM to support this key assumption is referred to as the "Clientele effect". The clientele effect states that a firm will attract stockholders whose preferences with respect to the payment pattern and stability of dividends corresponds to the firm's payment pattern and stability of dividends. Since the shareholder, or the clientele of the firm get what they expect, the value of the firm's stock is unaffected by changes in its dividend policy.

According to M.M. Model the market price of a share after dividend declared is calculated by apply the following formula;

$$P_0 = \frac{P_1 + D_1}{1 + K_c}$$

Where, =

P_0 = The prevailing market price of a share

R_c = The cost of Equity Capital

D_1 = Dividend to be received at the end of period one

P_1 = Market price of a share at the end of period one

The number of shares to be issued to implement the new projects is ascertained with the help of the following formula:

$$\Delta N = \frac{I - (E - nD_1)}{P_1}$$

Where,

n = Number of Shares outstanding at the beginning of the period.

ΔN = Change in the number of Shares outstanding during the period (i.e. No. of new shares to be issued).

I = Total investment amount required for capital budget.

E = Earnings of net income of the firm during the period.

2.3 LEGAL PROVISIONS OF DIVIDEND IN NIGERIA

Payment of Dividend:- Provisions of the Company and Allied Matter Act, 1990. Dividends are payable only out of the distribute profit of the Company

- S. 379.
- Dividend can be declared at the annual General meeting only on recommendation of the directors.
- Interim dividends may be paid as appear to the directors to be justified by the profit of the company.
- The general meeting can decrease the amount recommended by the directors but cannot increase it.
- Where the amount recommended by the directors is varied at the general meeting, it must be included in the relevant annual return.

Distribute profits out of which dividends can be paid include Sec 380.

- i. Profit from trading
- ii. Revenue reserves
- iii. Net realized profit on assets sold.

Restriction on declaration and payment of dividends Sec.381:

Dividends should not be declared or paid if there are reasonable grounds to believe that the company will be unable to pay its liabilities as they become due after payment of dividends.

Unclaimed Dividends -Sec 382

Where dividends are returned unclaimed, the company should send the list of beneficiaries with the notice of the next annual general meeting to members.

The company can invest the unclaimed dividend on expiration of three (3) months after sending the notice of the next annual general meeting to members.

- Where some members are omitted in the course of sending dividends advice to members due to company's fault, such dividends shall attract interest at the current bank rate from three months after the date they ought to have been posted.

The date of posting the dividends shall be deemed to be the date of payment and proof of whether they have been posted or not.

Reserve and capitalization sec 383

(i) Directors may set aside any amount as they think fit from the profit as reserve as this may be deployed in the business or re-invested in another venture or as carry forward

(ii) Company can capitalize reserve or undistributed profit on the recommendation of the directors

(iii) Reserve which ought to have been distributed as dividends to members can be used to pay-up the unpaid shares held by members

(iv) Company by resolution may decide which part of the reserve should be paid as cash or in shares and director shall give effect to such resolution

(v) Share premium account and capital redemption reserve fund may be applied in the paying up of unissued shares to be issued to members of the company as fully paid bonus shares
Employees shares and profit sharing: sec 384

(i) Where contract of service provides for an employee to be entitled to share in the profit of the company as an incentive, this shall remain in force whether or not the company declare dividends

Rights of shareholders to sue for dividend: sec 385

(i) Dividends shall be special debt due to and recoverable by shareholders within twelve years and actionable when declared

Liability of paying out dividend out of capital: 386

(i) All directors who knowing paid, or are party to the payment of dividend out of capital shall personally liable jointly and severally to refund the company any amount so paid

(ii) Such director shall have the right to recover dividend from shareholders who receive it with acknowledgement that the company had no power to pay it

2.4 FACTORS TO BE CONSIDERED BEFORE THE PAYMENT OF DIVIDENDS

Dividend policy determines the distribution of net cash flows generated from successful trading between payments to shareholders and reinvestment in the firm. Retained earnings are one of the most significant sources of funds for financing corporate growth, but dividends constitute the cash flows that accrue to shareholders. Before study of the different theories on dividend policy, understanding of the following considerations is necessary.

Transaction Costs: Transaction costs are of two different types.

- i. **Firm's transaction Costs:** The costs incurred in raising new capital are called floatation costs and it is ranging as high as 10 per cent of the Enterprise amount raised. The floatation costs associated with raising new funds give firms an incentive to avoid paying dividends.
- ii. **Shareholder's transaction Costs:** When a stock is sold, the investor must pay transaction costs of approximately 1 - 2 per cent of the share's value. The firm may be able to provide investor with dividend income at a lower transaction cost than if the investors provided income for themselves.

- **Shareholder's Income tax:** Dividend payments to individuals are subject to personal income taxation in the year received. At the time of selling the shares, the investor will be attracted with capital gains. By paying dividends, a corporation is forcing its stockholders to have to pay taxes earlier than they would if the dividends were not paid.
 - **Dividend Clientele:** Firms with different dividend policies will appeal to different kinds of investors with each group constituting a different dividend clientele. A dividend clientele is a group of investors favouring a particular kind of dividend policy. Low and zero tax payers appear to prefer high payout ratios, while high taxation groups prefer low dividends and expect to realize benefits through capital gains.
- Dividend Payout Ratio:

This is the fraction of net income a firm pays its stockholders as

Dividend.

The part of earnings not paid to investors is left for investment to provide for future growth. Investors seeking high current income and limited capital growth prefer companies with high Dividend payout ratio. However investors seeking capital growth may prefer low payout ratio because capital gains are taxed at lower rate. High growth firms in early life generally have low or zero payout ratios. As they mature, they tend to return more of the earnings back to investors. Note that dividend payout ratio is a reciprocal ratio to dividend ratio to dividend cover.

The payout ratio provides an idea of how well earnings support the dividend payment. It is worthy of note the matured companies tend to have higher payout

Dividend payout ratio is the dividend divided by the Net Income for the same period as follows:

$$\text{Dividend payout ratio} = \frac{\text{Dividend}}{\text{Net Income for the same period}}$$

*** Dividend Cover:**

This shows how many times over the profits could dividend be paid.

For example if the dividend cover is three (3) times this means, that the firm's profit attributable to the shareholders was three times the amount of dividend payout

The dividend cover is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Dividend Cover} = \frac{\text{Earnings per share}}{\text{Dividend per Share}}$$

Dividend cover is a measure of the ability of a company to maintain the level of dividend paid out. The higher the dividend cover the better the ability to maintain the dividends if profit drops. These needs to be looked at in the context of how stable a company's earnings are: a low level of dividend cover might be acceptable in a company with very stable profits, but the same level of cover at a company with volatile profits would indicate that dividends are at risk.

Because buyers of high yield shares tend to want a stable income.

Dividend cover is an important number for income investors.

Dividend cover is the inverse of the dividend payout ratio.

Dividend Signaling Hypothesis:

It has been observed that an increase in the price of the stock, while a dividend cut generally leads to a stock price decline. The companies, in practice appear to place great emphasis on last year's dividend when deciding the current year's dividend. Dividends tend to be more stable than earnings companies appear to pursue some long-term payout ratio and dividends are changed in line with expected future net cash flows.

Changes in dividend policy may convey information to the stock market. An increase in dividends is likely to be interpreted as good news and a cut as bad news. The complete skip off of a dividend is likely to be regarded as very bad news. The companies use this information channel to inform the investors.

According to the dividend signaling hypothesis, dividend changes provide an effective way of allowing management to convey believable information to the market about the firm's expected future cash flows.

By conveying the favourable information to the market in a believable way, the dividend decision may affect the value of the firm.

- **Divisible Profits:** All the profits of a company are not divisible. Only those profits which can be legally distributed in the form of dividend to the shareholders of the company are called as

"divisible profits", otherwise, it is treated as payment of dividend out of capital and the directors of the company are liable to make it good. Capital profits may only be used for dividend where the Articles permit and there is a bona fide revaluation of all the assets of the company and the profit has to be converted into cash i.e. realized.

- **Liquidity:** In order to pay dividend, a company requires cash and, therefore, the availability of cash resources within the company will be a factor in determining dividend payments. It is not necessarily mean a highly profitable situation but the company with large amounts of cash at its disposal. The liquidity position of the company will influence the dividend payout of a particular year.
- **Rate of expansion of business:** The rate of asset expansion needs to be taken into account. The more rapid the rate at which the firm is growing, the greater will be its needs for financing asset expansion. The greater the future need for funds, the more likely the firm is to retain earnings rather than pay them out. If a firm seeks to raise funds externally, natural sources are the present shareholders who already know the company, yet if earnings are paid out as dividends and are subjected to high personal income-tax rates, only a portion of the earnings would be available for reinvestment.
- **Rate of return:** Profit rate also influences the dividend/retention policy. The rate of return on assets determines the relative attractiveness of paying out earnings in the form of dividends to shareholders who will use them elsewhere, compared with the productivity of their use in the present enterprise.
- **Stability of earnings:** The stability of earnings also effects the decision. If earnings are relatively stable, a firm is better able to predict what its future earnings will be. A stable firm is, therefore, more likely to pay out a higher percentage of its earnings than is a firm with fluctuating earnings. The unstable firm is not certain that in subsequent years the hopes for earnings will realized, so it is more likely to retain a high proportion of earnings.
- **Contractual constraints:** When the company obtained loan funds from debenture holders or terms lending institutions, the terms of issues or contract of loan may contain restrictions on dividend payments designed to ensure that the firm will have enough funds to meet its obligations to the loan providers.

- Cost of external financing: The cost of external financing will have impact on the dividend payout of a company. In situations where the external funds are costlier, a firm may resort to low dividend payout and use the internal funds for financing its business.
- Degree of control: The management who wish to maintain close control over the firm will not much depend on the external sources of finance, and they maintain a low dividend payout policy and the fund generated from operations would be used for working capital and capital investment needs of the firm.
- Access of Capital Market: A firm who intends to raise further funds from the capital market for its expansion and diversification projects, therefore to attract the funds from the capital market, it has to maintain a liberal dividend policy. The investment decisions of a general investor will be influenced by the firm's dividend policies.
- General State of Economy: When state of economy is uncertain, both political and economic, the firm may maintain a low dividend payout policy, to withstand the business risks.

2.5 FORMS OF DIVIDEND POLICY

Constant Payout Ratio Policy -

- ❖ This method is known as "Constant Payout Ratio Method".
- ❖ This concept of stability of dividends means always paying a fixed percentage of the net earnings every year.
- ❖ The dividends vary from year to year, if earnings vary.
- ❖ The dividend policy is entirely based on company's ability to pay under this policy.
- ❖ The company follows a regular practice of retained earnings.
- ❖ For most firms, earnings are quite volatile, fluctuating with changes in the economy and firm's own special circumstances.
- ❖ Very few firms select this method.

Constant Dividend Rate Policy

- ❖ It is a most popular kind of dividend policy which advocates the payment of dividend at a constant rate, even when earnings vary from year to year.

- ❖ This may be possible only when the earnings pattern of the company does not show wide fluctuations.
- ❖ This policy is possible only through the maintenance of what is called 'Dividend Equalization Reserve'. Consequently, a company may invest funds equal to such reserves in some current investments so as to manage the liquidity of the necessary funds in times of need.
- ❖ Firms are generally careful to set the dividend at a sustainable level and raise it only when the firm can sustain the higher level. Occasionally, firms may cut dividends in adverse situations. Firms are against cutting dividends, because of the extremely unfavourable news it conveys to the market.

Multiple Dividend Increase Policy

- ❖ Some firms follow a policy of very frequent and very small dividend increases to give the illusion of movement and growth.
- ❖ The obvious hope behind such a policy is that the market rewards consistent increases.

Regular Dividend plus Extra Dividend Policy

- ❖ Some firms consciously divide their announced dividends into two portions: a regular dividend and an extra dividend.
- ❖ The regular dividend is the dividend that will continue at the announced level.
- ❖ The extra dividend payment will be made as circumstances permit.

Uniform Cash Dividend plus Bonus Shares Policy

- ❖ This policy is usually adopted in case of companies which have fluctuating earnings.
- ❖ Under this method, a minimum rate of dividend per share is paid in cash plus bonus shares are issued out of accumulated reserves.

- ❖ But the issue of bonus shares is not on annual basis. It depends upon the amount kept in reserve for a period say to 5 years.

Optimum Dividend Policy

Accepting that there is an optimum dividend policy, it is then necessary to find an approach to determine what the pay-out ratio should be. One approach would be to assess the net preferences for dividends over capital gains.

2.6 RELEVANCE AND IRRELEVANCE DIVIDEND THEORIES

Relevance Dividend Theory

The proponents of these theories especially J.B. Williams (1938) M.J. Gordon (1959) and Professor James E. Walter argued that dividends were all that mattered in the determination of share prices. This is based on the fundamental theory of share values. It assumes that:

- (i) the market value of a company's shares depends on the size of the dividends paid: the growth rate in dividends and shareholders' required rate of return
- (ii) The growth in dividends depends on how money is reinvested in the company, and the rate of earnings retention
- (iii) Shareholders will want their company to pursue how a retention policy maximizes the value of their shares

In Gordon's article on 'Dividends, Earnings and Stock Prices' he provided some empirical data to support the dividend supremacy hypothesis and the effect of dividend payout ratios on price earning ratios. This according to him was conclusive evidence that equity stock value was derived from dividends.

The dividend supremacy argument has good deal of practical appeal.

Basically an investor who plans to hold his shares in perpetuity except nothing other than dividends is paid; such an investor would be naive to ignore payout possibilities in his assessment.

In J. Walter version and assumption the firm finances all investments through retained earnings; firm maintains constant Internal Rate of Return (IRR) and Weighted Average Cost

of Capital (WACC), and all earnings are either distributed as dividend or reinvested internally immediately.

3.0 JUSTIFICATION FOR INVESTMENT IN A FIRM THAT MAINTAINS DIVIDEND POLICY

Dividend policy refers to the decision to payout earnings or to retain and reinvest them in the firm. There are three elements to dividend policy: (a) what fraction of earnings should be paid out on average over time; (b) whether the firm should maintain a stable dividend growth rate or vary its dividend payments from year to year based on its internal needs for cash; and (c) the amount the firm should pay in current dividends.

(i) The residual dividend model states that firms should pay dividends only when more earnings are available than needed to support the optimal capital budget.

(ii) The information content of dividends is a theory which holds that investors regard dividend changes as "signals" of management forecasts. Thus, when dividends are raised, this is viewed by investors as recognition by management as increase in future earnings. Therefore, if a firm's stock price increases with a dividend increase, the reason may not be investor preference for dividends, but expectations of higher future earnings. Conversely, a dividend reduction may signal that management is forecasting poor earnings in the future.

(iii) An extra dividend is a dividend paid in addition to the regular dividend when earnings permit. Firms with volatile earnings may have a low regular dividend that can be maintained even in low-profit (or high capital investment) years, and then supplement it with an extra dividend when excess funds are available.

(iv) High Dividends Increase Stock Value because dividends are more predictable and less risky than capital gains which should be discounted at a lower rate and dividend income should have a higher value than capital gains.

(v) Evidence indicates that a large, unexpected change in dividends can have significant impact on stock price.

(vi) As a firm's investment opportunities decrease, the dividend payout ratio should increase.

(vii) Investors may use the dividend policy as signal of information that is not easily accessible.

The dividend policy may be useful in assessing the company's long-term earnings prospects.

(viii) The "bird-in-the-hand" theory assumes that investors value a Naira of dividends more highly than a Naira of expected capital gains because the dividend yield component, D_1/PO , is less risky than the g component in the total expected return equation $k^s = D_1/PO + g$.

(ix) The dividend irrelevance theory holds that dividend policy has no effect on either the price of a firm's stock or its cost of capital.

The principal proponents of this view are Merton Miller and Franco Modigliani (MM). They prove their position in a theoretical sense, but only under strict assumptions, some of which are clearly not true in the real world.

4.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Dividend policy is an important component of maximizing shareholders' value and has always been an important part of shareholders' returns (Brave et al. 2005). It is therefore justifiable to invest in a firm with a policy of maintaining dividends when earnings are sufficiently high or corporate investment needs are low. This will enable firms to return cash to shareholders in order to satisfy personal income need; effectively manage the company's cash needs and capital structure and credibly signals to shareholders about future and long term earnings prospects.

At the same time other investors may want such earnings from investment to be reinvested for capital appreciation. Aside those who pay heavy tax do not want the earnings realized from investment distributed in form of dividend to avoid payment of tax now most especially if the tax rate is high. There could be other investors who invest because they want to make name in future by having majority share holding thereby having a say in the running of such a business, while others may invest for self actualization purposes. In any of the above scenario the general purpose of investing in a firm is wealth maximization.

Dividends are primary vehicles for returning cash or enhancing the value/wealth of shareholders. It will be therefore worthwhile to give the following recommendations:

(i) A company should choose a payout ratio that transfers the majority of its free cash flow to shareholders as dividends. In doing so a company should avoid a dividend payout that is too high, because a high payout ratio reduces its financial flexibility.

(ii) Company should be able to strike a balance by making provision for those who are interested in capital gains. This could be done by issuing out shares in place of cash dividend.

(ii) Dividend policy should be viewed as part of the integral financial plan, since shareholders wealth is maximized through an effective investment strategy.

(iii) Dividends should be used as a primary vehicle to distribute cash to shareholders. Once a company's operating plan has been appropriately financed dividend should be the primary source of cash flow paid out to shareholders.

(iv) Dividend should be used to appropriately signal shareholders and management's confidence about future earnings prospects. It should not only be based on past earnings.

(v) Dividends should be increased when a company's earnings are sufficiently high. However, since the market will focus primarily on earnings growth in years of strong earnings, firms can temper their dividend increases in these years by lowering payout. In average years, a company's earnings and dividend increases

- should be similar. In years of weak earnings, assuming the company is positive about the future, the dividend can signal confidence.

(vi) Firms should avoid a high dividend payout that will provide little flexibility. It is better to set the dividend payout ratio below the likely payout ratio.

Firms should avoid dividend reductions or elimination, since these actions typically lead to significant drop in a firm's stock price and sends clear negative message to the market about future prospects

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